

IMPLEMENTATION OF TVET PROGRAM: INPUT TO ACTION PLAN TOWARDS ENHANCED PROGRAM IMPLEMENTATION

Rosacris A. Siena

Graduate School, Marinduque State University, Marinduque, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study assesses the implementation of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) programs from the viewpoints of trainers and trainees. Data was collected from 50 trainers and 367 trainees across 13 TESDA institutions using a 65-item questionnaire. The mean and thematic analysis were used to answer research questions, and an independent t-test with a 0.05 significance level was employed to evaluate the null hypothesis. The study found overall positive feedback on the implementation of Curriculum Design, Training Delivery, Training Facilities, and Trainers' Qualifications. However, perceptions varied on the degree of implementation of Tools, Equipment, and Materials, with trainers seeing it as "implemented" and trainees as "fully implemented." Challenges included limited industry engagement, insufficient resources, late material delivery, space constraints, and cost issues. Solutions proposed include industry collaboration, sharing of modules, establishing partnership with industry, utilizing multi-purpose spaces, and availing free online training.

Keywords: *Assessment of TVET programs, Curriculum Design, Training Delivery, Tools, Equipment, and Materials, Training Facilities, Trainers' Qualifications, Coping strategies and challenges*

INTRODUCTION

There is an increasing need for a competent workforce to adapt to new technology, foster innovation, and support economic development in today's fast-changing global

marketplace. Technical Vocational Education and Training or TVET programs are essential in preparing people with the knowledge and skills to satisfy these demands. These courses offer hands-on training applicable to the workplace, preparing students for various careers and improving their employment prospects.

The foundation of any country's economic and social progress is its knowledge and skills (Goel, 2010), and the development of the talented and creative workforce required for the rapidly evolving technology workforce depends heavily on Technical Vocational Education and Training (Afeti, 2010). TVET programs are essential for equipping Filipinos with the knowledge and abilities required to work in various industries. Students can improve their technical skills, trade competencies, and entrepreneurial aptitude through formal and informal education and training provided by the TVET system.

According to Morales (2019), the rising demand of the competitive labor market and the persistent problem of unemployment and underemployment have raised several TVET issues and concerns. Are graduates provided with quality education and training in preparation for their employment? Do the graduates possess the competencies that employers seek? Are program interventions and other support activities capable of increasing graduates' employability?

Nations such as South Korea, Taiwan, and Japan make significant investments in vocational education systems to tackle the issues caused by a lack of skilled labor (Tilak, 2003). Some nations have implemented strict quotas and admission exams to control university enrollment rates and promote TVET system enrollment. They have had faster industrial and economic growth due to a talented and dynamic middle-class workforce.

Through an empirical survey, Liu et al. (2015) found that China's vocational education policies must be implemented better. Vocational colleges and enterprises and other industry stakeholders should deeply participate in making vocational education policy, creating a social atmosphere to pay attention to vocational education, and strengthening propaganda of the implementation of occupation education policy.

As Philippine society values degrees and diplomas of higher education more than TVET, the latter is generally regarded as inferior education, and the community needs to fully realize the importance of TVET to the labor market. Besides, structural unemployment caused by mismatched supply and demand is found in the Philippine labor market. The qualification rate of TVET graduates reaches 88.0%, but their employment rate is still at a low rate of 60.9% (NTESDP, 2018). Graduates of TVET face a limited employment market, primarily caused by the poor quality of TVET and the irrelevance of school learning with enterprise work practices. One of the main issues is the low employability of Philippine TVET graduates, which is only 65% (NTESDP, 2018). TVET providers are frequently accused of offering and generating low-quality skills and technical education. This reality is reflected in the labor market, which is defined by a 70:30 ratio of low-value work to mid- to high-value work (NTESDP, 2018).

The implementation of TVET programs can be assessed by looking at the learning outcomes, getting input from participants and stakeholders, and conducting assessments to establish the program's overall success and pinpoint areas that need improvement. To ensure the success and relevance of the TVET program, it emphasizes the necessity for ongoing monitoring, review, and modification. It entails making the necessary alterations and enhancements to the program's structure, delivery strategy, and evaluation methodology using the feedback and information acquired during the evaluation phase (Odiorne, 1968).

The importance of evaluations from both trainers and trainees lies in their mutual accountability and the opportunity for continuous improvement. Both stakeholders have unique perspectives and insights to offer, contributing to a more holistic understanding of the training program's effectiveness. By actively involving both trainers and trainees in evaluations, the overall quality of the training experience can be enhanced, fostering a collaborative learning environment.

In an evaluation of the Strengthened Technical and Vocational Education Program-Competency Based Curriculum (STVEP-CBC) implementation in Region X, Northern Mindanao, Alfred et al. (2012) recommended that more frequent monitoring be done to ensure that the program is carried out effectively and efficiently. However, there are limited Philippine TVET program evaluations that can be found in the literature. In fact evaluation in TESDA Marinduque is very rare and no up to date evaluation of TVET program implementation is available. Hence, this study was conducted to provide input to an action plan towards enhanced program implementation in TESDA Marinduque.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the implementation of the TVET program as input to an action plan for enhanced program implementation.

Specifically, it looked for responses to the following queries:

1. What is the level of implementation of TVET Programs as assessed by the trainers and trainees in terms of?
 - 1.1 Curriculum Design;
 - 1.2 Training Delivery;
 - 1.3 Tools, Equipment, and Materials;
 - 1.4 Training Facilities; and
 - 1.5 Trainers' Qualifications
2. Is there any significant difference in the trainers' and trainees' assessments of the implementation of TVET programs?
3. What problems do the trainers and trainees encounter in the implementation of TVET programs?
4. What coping strategies do trainers use to address the challenges faced by themselves and their trainees during the implementation of TVET programs?

5. What strategies could be proposed to enhance program implementation as part of the action plan?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the province of Marinduque, specifically in the five municipalities (Boac, Mogpog, Sta. Cruz, Torrijos, and Gasan) where the TVET Institutions are located. It involved three TESDA Technology Institutions (TTIs) and 10 TESDA-Accredited Schools.

Research Population and Sample

The facts and data needed for the study were gathered from the trainers and trainees covered from January 2022 - June 2023 training period of three TESDA Technology Institutions (TTIs), namely the Buyabod School of Arts and Trade (BSAT), Torrijos Poblacion School of Arts and Trades (TPSAT) and Provincial Training Center (PTC) and 10 TESDA Accredited schools, such as the Marinduque Manpower and Trade Skills Institute, Inc. (MMTSI), Santa Cruz Institute (Marinduque), Inc. (SCI), Marinduque Technical Vocational Institute Inc. (MTVI), Marinduque Technical Training Center Inc. (MTTCI), AGREA Agricultural Communities International Foundation, Inc., DMDC Farm, Mogpog International Culinary School (MICS), and Regalia's Learning and Training Center, Inc. (RLTC), Agsikapin Technological Training Institute, Inc., and KALUPPA Foundation, Inc., in Marinduque were used as the respondents of the study.

Stratified Random Sampling is a method used in statistical research to ensure that the sample accurately represents the population by dividing the population into district subgroups or strata. Each stratum is then sampled independently using a random sampling technique. In the context of selecting trainees in TVET institutions, the proportionate and disproportionate stratification formulas $\{\text{sample size}/\text{population size}\}$ (stratum size) were used to determine the number of trainees from each institution.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study are trainers and trainees of the three TESDA Technology Institutions (TTIs) and 10 TESDA Accredited schools in the province of Marinduque.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before conducting the survey, the researcher sought permission from the schools involved. Before being distributed, the instrument is validated by various individuals knowledgeable about the execution of TVET programs in Marinduque. Data collection has been made possible through the assistance and participation of trainers from each

institution. At the start of the data-gathering process, the researcher outlined the study's purpose, objectives, and expected outcomes. Following this, respondents received a consent form detailing confidentiality measures and their rights. The data collection methods, including surveys and interviews, were explained, with a focus on confidentiality and privacy. Respondents were assured that data would be stored securely and used solely for research. Maintaining clear communication fosters trust and encourages participants to ask questions. Then, they were given questionnaires to complete at their convenience. After a week, the researcher collected the questionnaires from each institution, concluding this phase of the study.

The primary research tool used in the study is the personal self-made questionnaire which the researcher administered to the 13 TVET Institutions in Marinduque.

Research Instrument

The study used a series of questionnaires to collect pertinent data that would answer the study's challenge. A self-made questionnaire was utilized to collect the data required for the study's completion. The researcher sought approval from four specialists to validate the research instrument: Jezreel R. Ferrer-Assistant Professor II (BSAT), Norinel R. Pielago-Senior TESD Specialist (PTC-Marinduque), Olimpio Pacheco Jr. - Senior TESD Specialist (PTC-Marinduque), and Teresita A. Ferrer-Associate Professor IV (TPSAT) who are experts in the implementation of TVET programs.

First, the study determined the level of TVET program implementation regarding curriculum design, training delivery, tools, equipment, materials, training facilities, and trainer qualifications. The following Likert scale was used to assess the program implementation.

Table 1.

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
4	3.51-4.00	Fully Implemented	100% implementation
3	2.51-3.50	Implemented	More than 50% implementation but not 100%
2	1.51-2.50	Moderately Implemented	Less than 50% implementation
1	1.00-1.50	Not Implemented	0% implementation

Second, the researcher identified the challenges faced by trainers and trainees in implementing TVET programs, along with the coping strategies employed by the trainers. The final draft incorporates the ideas and recommendations provided by the validators.

Statistical Treatment and Data Analysis

The following statistical procedures were used for data analysis: mean score, thematic analysis, and t-tests. The t-test compares trainers' and trainees' assessment in terms of TVET program implementation.

As a result, the data for SOP 1 on the level of implementation of TVET programs as assessed by trainers and trainees was measured using Mean. Meanwhile, for SOP 2 on the significant difference in trainers' and trainees' assessments of TVET program implementation, the t-test was used for the comparison.

Moreover, SOP 3 focused on the challenges experienced by trainers and trainees, while SOP 4 examined into the coping strategies employed by trainers to address the issues faced by both themselves and their trainees during the implementation of TVET Programs, utilizing thematic analysis.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study evaluated the implementation of TVET Programs of three TTIs and 10 TESDA-Accredited schools in the province of Marinduque. The study focuses on the level of implementation of TVET programs in terms of curriculum design, training delivery, tools, materials, equipment, training facilities, and trainer qualifications.

Moreover, the problems that trainers and trainees encountered in implementing TVET programs and the coping strategies to address the issues are also discussed. The population involved herein are 50 trainers and 367 trainees during the training period of January 2022 to June 2023.

RESULTS

Table 2.

Level of TVET Programs' Implementation as Assessed by the Trainers and Trainees

No.	Indicator	Trainee			Trainer			Total		
		Mean	SD	Description	Mean	SD	Description	Mean	SD	Description
1	Curriculum Design	3.78	0.228	Fully Implemented	3.72	0.140	Fully Implemented	3.77	0.220	Fully Implemented
2	Training Delivery	3.65	0.322	Fully Implemented	3.57	0.268	Fully Implemented	3.64	0.317	Fully Implemented
3	Tools, Equipment and Materials	3.66	0.295	Fully Implemented	3.47	0.284	Implemented	3.63	0.300	Fully Implemented

4	Training Facilities	3.59	0.312	Fully Implemented	3.58	0.256	Fully Implemented	3.59	0.305	Fully Implemented
5	Trainer's Qualification	3.68	0.241	Fully Implemented	3.70	0.126	Fully Implemented	3.68	0.230	Fully Implemented
	Grand Mean	3.67	0.203	Fully Implemented	3.62	0.139	Fully Implemented	3.67	0.197	Fully Implemented

Legend: 1.00-1.50=Not Implemented (0% implementation); 1.51-2.50=moderately Implemented (Less than 50% implementation); 2.51-3.50=Implemented (More than 50% implementation but not 100%); 3.51-4.00=fully Implemented (100% implementation)

Table 3.

Significant Differences between the Implementation of TVET Programs as Assessed by the Trainers and Trainee Respondents

Curriculum Design	3.192	.075	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Training Delivery	2.606	.107	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Tools, Equipment, and Materials	17.731	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Training Facilities	.043	.835	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Trainers' Qualification	.465	.496	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Implementation of TVET Programs	2.864	.091	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 4.

Problems Faced by Trainers and Trainees in TVET Program Implementation

Areas of Concern	Problems Encountered
1. Curriculum Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of local industry and ineffective job placement support for the graduates
2. Training Delivery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited selection of books and journals Late delivery of training materials and supplies
3. Tools, Equipment, and Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability and completeness of training tools, equipment, and materials.
4. Training Facilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Space limitations
5. Trainers' Qualification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low number of higher qualification holders Cost/financial constraints

Table 5.

Coping Strategies used by trainers and trainees when faced with problems during TVET program implementation

Areas of Concern	Problems Encountered	COPING STRATEGIES
1. Curriculum Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of local industry and ineffective job placement support for the graduates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborate with local industries to secure on-job-training placements for students. Establish formal agreements or memorandums of understanding (MOUs) that outline the terms and expectations for the OJT program.
2. Training Delivery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited selection of books and journals Late delivery of training materials and supplies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sharing of modules Display training materials visually using PowerPoint presentation Conduct a thorough inventory strictly and regularly.
3. Tools, Equipment, and Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability and completeness of training tools, equipment, and materials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct a thorough inventory strictly and regularly.
4. Training Facilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Space limitations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilization of Multi-Purpose Spaces Implementation of Flexible Scheduling
5. Trainers' Qualification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low number of higher qualification holders Cost/financial constraints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Avail free online training and seminar External Training and Certification Programs

Table 6.

Summary of the Research Problems Encountered, Coping and Proposed Strategies

Areas of Concern	Problems Encountered	COPING STRATEGIES	PROPOSED STRATEGIES
1. Curriculum Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of local industry and ineffective job placement support for the graduates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborate with local industries to secure on-job-training placements for students. Establish formal agreements or memorandums of understanding (MOUs) that outline the terms and expectations for the OJT program. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intensify the identification of local industry for the deployment of on-job-training (OJT) Alumni Engagement
2. Training Delivery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited selection of books and journals Late delivery of training materials and supplies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sharing of modules Display training materials visually using PowerPoint presentation Conduct a thorough inventory strictly and regularly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invest in digital resources and online databases Utilization of Online Learning Management Systems (LMS) Early submission of purchase request prior to the training schedule.
3. Tools, Equipment, and Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability and completeness of training tools, equipment, and materials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct a thorough inventory strictly and regularly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish partnership with industry
4. Training Facilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Space limitations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilization of Multi-Purpose Spaces Implementation of Flexible Scheduling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) for Off-Campus Physical Facilities
5. Trainers' Qualification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low number of higher qualification holders Cost/financial constraints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Avail free online training and seminar External Training and Certification Programs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide financial assistance or time off for employees to pursue these opportunities.

Table 7.

Key Steps in Implementing TVET Program’s Enhancement

Areas of Concerns	Proposed Strategies	Key Steps to Implement
1. Curriculum Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intensify the identification of local industry for the deployment of on-job-training (OJT) Alumni Engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct an analysis to identify local industries that align with the institution's programs and courses. Establish connections and partnerships with industry leaders through networking events, industry associations, or alumni networks. Engage in dialogue with industry representatives to understand their needs, requirements, and potential opportunities for OJT placements. Collaborate with industry partners to develop a framework for OJT, including the duration, learning objectives, evaluation criteria, and potential employment opportunities.
2. Training Delivery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invest in digital resources and online databases Utilization of Online Learning Management Systems (LMS) Early submission of purchase request prior to the training schedule. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the current resources available and identify gaps in digital resources and online databases. Allocate a budget for the acquisition or subscription of digital resources and online databases relevant to the curriculum and training needs. Research and select reputable providers or platforms that offer comprehensive and up-to-date resources. Collaborate with the IT department or external vendors to implement the necessary infrastructure and systems for accessing and managing digital resources.
3. Tools, Equipment, and Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish partnership in industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify relevant industries/potential partners Establish communication channels Define the goals and objectives of the partnership. Develop a partnership agreement.
4. Training Facilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) for Off-Campus Physical Facilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify potential off-campus physical facilities that can be used for training sessions or workshops. Reach out to the owners or administrators of these facilities to discuss the possibility of establishing a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA). Collaboratively draft the MOA, clearly outlining the terms, expectations, and responsibilities of both parties. Seek legal review and approval of the MOA to ensure compliance with relevant laws and regulations. Regularly review and update the MOA as needed to reflect any changes or improvements.
5. Trainers’ Qualification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide financial assistance or time off for employees to pursue these opportunities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a policy or program that outlines the criteria and process for providing financial assistance or time off for employees to pursue external training and certification programs. Allocate a budget specifically for supporting employee development and training opportunities. Regularly assess the impact and effectiveness of the program and make adjustments as necessary.

Table 8.

Input in the Action Plan for TVET Programs' Enhancement

Areas of Concern	Objectives	Tasks	Expected Output
1. Curriculum Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthen partnerships with industry, government, and other stakeholders to enhance the effectiveness and reach of TVET programs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify potential industry and government partners. Arrange meetings with potential partners to discuss collaboration opportunities. Develop joint initiatives, such as internships, guest lectures, and curriculum development. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Established partnerships with industry and government organizations that can contribute to the effectiveness and reach of TVET programs. Create opportunities for students to gain practical experience through internships, access industry expertise through guest lectures, and align the curriculum with industry needs.
2. Training Delivery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance training delivery through digital resources and online platforms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research and select appropriate online platforms for training delivery. Develop or source digital resources relevant to the curriculum. Train instructors on how to use these platforms and resources effectively. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identified and implemented online platforms that enhance training delivery, allowing for flexible learning options and access to digital resources. Equipped instructors with the necessary skills to effectively utilize online platforms and digital resources in their teaching, enhancing the quality of training delivery.
3. Tools, equipment, and materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve tools, equipment, and facilities for hands-on training. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate the current state of tools, equipment, and facilities. Identify and procure necessary upgrades or replacements. Ensure all users are trained on safe and effective use of the new tools and equipment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acquired updated tools, equipment, and facilities that meet the needs of the training programs, ensuring a conducive learning environment.
4. Training Facilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthen the overall infrastructure of TVET training institutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct a thorough assessment of the existing infrastructure. Develop a plan for necessary upgrades or additions. Implement the infrastructure improvement plan. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Created a roadmap for infrastructure improvements, addressing identified gaps and enhancing the overall infrastructure of TVET training institutions.
5. Trainers' Qualification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance trainers' qualifications and professional development. Enhance the capacity of TVET instructors through regular training and professional development. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify areas where trainers need further qualifications or development. Arrange for relevant training programs, workshops, or courses. Monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of these professional development activities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identified specific areas where trainers require additional qualifications or professional development to enhance their teaching capabilities. Provided trainers with opportunities for further qualifications and professional development, enabling them to deliver high-quality training.

DISCUSSION

Table 2 displays the findings of the assessment of trainers and trainees, which shows the same outcome for the overall implementation of TVET programs. Trainee respondents assessed a grand mean value of 3.67 with a standard deviation of 0.203, while trainer respondents evaluated a grand mean value of 3.62 with a standard deviation of 0.139. With a standard deviation of 0.197 and a combined mean rating of 3.67, the two are considered "fully implemented." The two respondents agreed that curriculum design, training delivery, tools, materials and equipment, training facilities, and trainer qualifications had been "fully implemented."

Curriculum design has a strong alignment between the designed curriculum and the perceived needs of the trainees. This alignment is essential for effective knowledge transfer and skill development during training delivery. Competency-Based Training (CBT) serves as the foundation of training facilities, encompassing various key areas such as the Practical Work Area, Distance Learning Area, Learners' Resource Area, Institutional Assessment Area, Trainer's Resource Area, Quality Control Area, Support Service Area, and Contextual Learning Area.

Creating an atmosphere that is conducive to effective learning is imperative in the realm of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET). The role of TVET teachers, trainers, or instructors is dominant in the TVET industry as they are instrumental in facilitating the learning process and imparting technical skills to trainees. Therefore, it is essential to ensure that these instructors are well-equipped and adequately prepared to deliver high-quality training that meets the standards of competency-based education.

By focusing on the continuous professional development of TVET instructors, providing them with the necessary resources, and fostering a supportive environment for their growth, institutions can enhance the overall quality of training delivery and ultimately contribute to the development of a skilled workforce that meets the demands of the industry. The commitment to empowering instructors and enhancing their capabilities is a crucial aspect of ensuring the effectiveness and success of competency-based training programs in the TVET sector. Williams et al. (2021) underscore the significance of continuous professional development for TVET trainers. Institutions that offer regular training opportunities, workshops, conferences, and networking events for trainers create a culture of lifelong learning and ensure trainers stay updated with emerging trends, technologies, and teaching methodologies.

The difference in the obtained mean value from the evaluation of the two groups of respondents resulted in the specific findings observed in the tools, equipment, and materials considered. The grand mean suggests that, on average, both trainees and trainers perceive a high level of implementation in tools, equipment, and materials. However, trainers' ratings indicate potential room for improvement or further collaboration.

The grand mean across all indicators reflects high satisfaction and consensus between trainees and trainers regarding the full implementation of TVET programs. The findings suggest a generally positive perception of the implemented TVET programs, with all indicators showing high fulfilment. Consistency between the perspectives of trainees and trainers is crucial, indicating a shared understanding of the effectiveness of various program components. While the overall implementation is strong, the slightly lower trainer rating in the "Tools, Equipment, and Materials" category may warrant further investigation and potential resource provision and utilization improvements.

These findings are encouraging and suggest that the TVET programs successfully meet their objectives, as trainers and trainees perceived. Regular assessments and open communication channels can further contribute to the continuous improvement of these programs, suggesting that the programs are effectively meeting the needs and expectations of both parties.

According to the data displayed in Table 3, the p-values for the variables are greater than the significance level of 0.05, which implies that there is no significant difference in the assessment of trainers and trainees, except for the tools, equipment and materials. The lack of significance suggests no statistically significant difference in how trainers and trainees assess the implementation of curriculum design, training delivery, training facilities, and trainer qualifications. Similar perceptions between the two groups indicate a shared understanding of the effectiveness of curriculum design, training delivery, training facilities, and trainer qualifications.

However, the respondents have differing views on how tools, equipment, and materials are used in the TVET program implementation. It suggests that the null hypothesis is not supported. It also indicates that participants showed up and expressed their opinions about the study, as the results reveal notable variations. Perhaps the disparities between the two respondents' evaluations stem from their differing perspectives on how they utilized the tools, equipment, and materials—whether they were complete—if they were using.

Moreover, the results imply that rejecting the null hypothesis would enlighten the researcher to arrive at vigorous recommendations that would enhance the implementation of TVET Programs regarding tools, equipment, and materials. To provide effective teaching and learning in TVET establishments, instructional resources in many developing countries still require improvement (Wondaferew, 2012). For example, in Nigeria, the non-use of instructional materials in TVET institutions has impeded teachers' and students' ability to teach and learn (Okwudishu, 2005; Gambari & Okoli, 2007).

Table 4 shows the problems encountered by the trainers and trainees in implementing TVET programs. In the research conducted, the researcher identified problems and challenges encountered by both trainers and trainees within the training environment. Through a thorough analysis of the data collected, the researcher identified a range of issues that were commonly shared among the two groups. To streamline the findings, responses that were similar and common were consolidated.

The trainers and trainees who answered “Moderately implemented” in each indicators interviewed by the researcher about the problems faced in implementing TVET programs in terms of curriculum design, it became clear that there was a lack of local industry and ineffective job placement support for the graduates where trainees could apply their newly acquired knowledge and skills to use and practice, as well as ineffective job placement support. This suggests that the curriculum might not be aligned with the needs and demands of the local job market. Graduates may lack the skills and knowledge required by local industries, leading to difficulties in finding employment. Additionally, if there's inadequate support for job placement, graduates may struggle to secure positions even if they have the necessary skills.

In delivering training as part of implementing TVET programs the results showed that the school library had a limited selection of books and journals and the training materials and supplies were delivered late. A limited selection of learning resources can hinder the quality of training provided. Without access to a wide range of books and journals, trainees may miss out on valuable information and perspectives, limiting their understanding of the subject matter. Delays in delivering training materials and supplies can disrupt the learning process and impact the effectiveness of training programs. It may lead to missed learning opportunities and frustration among both trainees and trainers.

Furthermore, space constraints were stressed when the researcher interviewed trainers and trainees about the challenges they faced when implementing TVET programs in relation to training facilities. The implementation of training programs may be affected by inadequate space, which may limit the kinds of activities that can be carried out and the number of trainees who may take participation. The standard quality of instruction and the comfort of the trainees may be influenced by overcrowded spaces.

In terms of trainer qualifications, it revealed that there were low number of higher qualification holders and cost/financial constraints. The qualifications of trainers directly impact the quality of education provided. A shortage of trainers with higher qualifications may result in less effective teaching, as they may lack in-depth knowledge or expertise in their respective fields. Financial limitations may hinder the recruitment or retention of highly qualified trainers. Additionally, budget constraints might restrict opportunities for professional development, preventing trainers from staying updated with the latest industry trends and teaching methodologies.

The trainees can employ training tools, equipment, and materials because they disagree with the real training schedules, according to several of the trainees the researcher talked with. Simultaneously, the trainers stated that the late purchase request for training as well as the delayed delivery of supplies and materials indicate that the training tools, equipment, and materials must be finished and made available. Insufficient tools, equipment, and materials may hinder experiential training. Trainees may find it difficult to gain the practical skills that are frequently necessary for success in a variety of occupations if they do not have access to the relevant resources.

Addressing these concerns requires a comprehensive approach involving collaboration between educational institutions, industry stakeholders, and policymakers. It may involve curriculum revisions to align with industry needs, investment in resources and facilities, professional development opportunities for trainers, and improved support for student job placement.

Table 5 shows the coping strategies employed by trainers to address the issues faced by both themselves and their trainees during the implementation of TVET Programs in terms of curriculum design, training delivery, training tools, equipment and materials, training facilities and trainer's qualification.

In terms of curriculum design, trainers and trainees encountered problem that there was a lack of local industry and ineffective job placement support for the graduates where trainees could apply their newly acquired knowledge and skills to use and practice, as well as ineffective job placement support. Collaborate with local industries to secure on-job-training placements for students and establish formal agreements or memorandums of understanding (MOUs) that outline the terms and expectations for the OJT program which includes the duration of the training, learning objectives, evaluation criteria, and possible employment opportunities after completion are some of trainer's coping strategies.

Moreover, in training delivery, the results showed that the school library had a limited selection of books and journals that training materials and supplies were delivered late. As for the trainer's coping strategies, trainees share modules, display training materials visually using PowerPoint presentation. When it comes to the late delivery of materials and supplies, trainers conduct thorough inventory strictly and regularly.

Furthermore, the problems encountered during the implementation of TVET Programs regarding training facilities, it revealed space limitations. As to the trainer's coping strategies, utilization of multi-purpose spaces and implementation of flexible scheduling.

During the interviews conducted with trainees who indicated a moderate level of implementation, they expressed that while they were able to utilize the training tools, equipment, and materials provided to them, they also conveyed a sense of inadequacy regarding the availability and sufficiency of these resources. At the same time, the trainers mentioned that the training tools, equipment, and materials need to be completed and should be available during class time. This problem occurs because of late purchase request for training resources and the delayed delivery of materials and supplies. As part of the trainers' coping strategies, they conduct a thorough inventory strictly and regularly.

Furthermore, the study highlighted a scarcity of trainers with higher qualifications, attributing this shortage to cost-related financial constraints. In response to these challenges, trainers have adopted coping strategies such as engaging in free online training and seminars, as well as participating in external training and certification programs. These initiatives are aimed at enhancing their skills, adapting to evolving pedagogical methods, and improving their overall capabilities in the training domain.

The following problems encountered and coping strategies are plotted in Table 6 and mapped with the proposed strategies. In the area of curriculum design, one of the problems encountered is the lack of local industry and ineffective job placement support for graduates. To cope with this, a strategy is to collaborate with local industries to secure on-the-job-training (OJT) placements for students. By engaging in partnerships with industry leaders, educational institutions can provide students with practical experience and exposure to real-world work environments. Additionally, establishing formal agreements or Memorandums of Understanding (MOUs) can outline the terms and expectations for the OJT program, including the duration of the training, learning objectives, evaluation criteria, and potential employment opportunities after completion. This ensures a clear framework for both the educational institution and industry partner, fostering a mutually beneficial relationship.

In terms of training delivery, problems such as limited selection of books and journals and late delivery of training materials and supplies can be addressed through various coping strategies. Sharing of modules can help overcome the limited selection of resources by leveraging the expertise and materials available within the institution. Displaying training materials visually using PowerPoint presentations can enhance the delivery of content and engage learners. Conducting a thorough inventory strictly and regularly can help identify any gaps in training materials and ensure timely procurement or replenishment. Investing in digital resources and online databases can provide access to a wider range of materials, while implementing an Online Learning Management System can facilitate efficient distribution and access to training materials. Additionally, early submission of purchase requests prior to the training schedule can help mitigate delays in the delivery of necessary materials and supplies.

When it comes to tools, equipment, and materials, ensuring their availability and completeness is crucial. Conducting a thorough inventory strictly and regularly can help identify any missing or outdated items and facilitate timely procurement or replacement. Similarly, establish partnership with industry can help prevent delays in acquiring the necessary tools, equipment, and materials. By implementing these strategies, educational institutions can ensure that trainers and trainees have access to the resources they need for effective training delivery.

Space limitations in training facilities can pose challenges, but coping strategies can be implemented. Utilizing multi-purpose spaces within the facility can help maximize available space by repurposing areas such as conference rooms or cafeterias for training sessions when not in use for their primary functions. Implementing flexible scheduling allows for better utilization of space by accommodating multiple groups or departments at different times or on different days. Additionally, establishing Memorandums of Agreement (MOAs) for Off-Campus Physical Facilities can provide additional space when needed, either through rented conference rooms or partnerships with other organizations that have larger training facilities.

The low number of higher qualification holders among trainers can be addressed by availing free online training and seminars, which can provide opportunities for

professional development. External training and certification programs can also be explored, where employees can pursue advanced qualifications or certifications to enhance their skills. Providing financial assistance or time off for employees to pursue these opportunities can help overcome cost or financial constraints.

Overall, these proposed strategies aim to address the problems encountered in curriculum design, training delivery, tools, equipment, and materials, training facilities, and trainers' qualifications. By implementing these strategies, educational institutions can enhance the quality of training and better prepare graduates for the demands of the industry.

These strategies aligns to the TESDA Impact Evaluation Survey 2012, which reveals that TESDA-administered schools should provide more effort and purposive policies for interventions to strengthen the employment rate of its graduates. Policy interventions include:

- Expanding apprenticeship programs to ensure employment in the future,
- Utilizing Online Learning Management Systems (LMS),
- Continuous financial support in the provision of modern facilities and equipment and;
- Provide training and professional development opportunities

Table 7 presents the key steps to enhance the implementation of TVET programs. These address critical aspects of the program, including curriculum design, training delivery, tools, equipment and materials, training facilities, and trainer qualifications.

The proposed strategies aim to address key concerns within the educational institution systematically. For curriculum design, the institution plans to identify local industries relevant to its programs, fostering partnerships and dialogue to tailor on-the-job-training (OJT) opportunities. Similarly, in training delivery, emphasis is placed on investing in digital resources, including Online Learning Management Systems (LMS), and ensuring timely procurement of necessary materials. Clear guidelines and procedures are established for purchase requests in tools, equipment, and materials, while off-campus facilities are secured through Memorandums of Agreement (MOAs).

Finally, the institution commits to supporting trainers' qualification through financial assistance, communication of available support, and regular program assessment for continuous improvement. These strategies collectively aim to enhance curriculum relevance, resource accessibility, and trainer qualification, ensuring a comprehensive approach to educational quality and effectiveness.

Table 8 provides input for enhancing TVET programs to bridge the gap between education and the workforce. The focus is on improving skills and competencies to address unemployment, promote sustainable development, and support job growth in a dynamic economy through the expansion of TVET programs.

In curriculum design, fostering partnerships with industry, government, and other stakeholders is dominant. By engaging with these entities, TVET programs can ensure alignment with current industry needs and practices. This involves identifying potential partners, initiating discussions, and collaboratively developing initiatives such as internships and curriculum enhancements. Through these partnerships, students can gain practical experience, access industry expertise, and ultimately benefit from a more relevant and effective curriculum.

In training delivery, leveraging digital resources and online platforms can significantly enhance accessibility and effectiveness. Researching and selecting appropriate online platforms, developing digital resources, and providing instructor training are key tasks. By implementing these tools effectively, TVET programs can offer flexible learning options and ensure access to relevant materials, thereby improving the overall quality of training delivery.

Improving tools, equipment, and facilities for hands-on training is crucial for providing students with a conducive learning environment. This involves evaluating current resources, procuring necessary upgrades or replacements, and ensuring proper training for users. Up-to-date tools and facilities enable students to develop practical skills effectively, preparing them for real-world scenarios.

Strengthening the overall infrastructure of TVET training institutions is essential for long-term sustainability and effectiveness. Conducting assessments, developing improvement plans, and implementing necessary upgrades or additions are key steps. By addressing infrastructure gaps, institutions can enhance the overall learning environment and support the delivery of high-quality training programs.

Enhancing trainers' qualifications and professional development is vital for ensuring the delivery of high-quality education. Identifying areas for improvement, arranging relevant training programs, and monitoring effectiveness are crucial tasks. By investing in trainers' development, TVET programs can ensure that instructors are equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to deliver effective training and support student success. By focusing on these areas of concern and implementing the outlined objectives and tasks, TVET programs can enhance their effectiveness, relevance, and reach, ultimately better preparing students for success in their chosen fields.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the researcher arrived at the following conclusion, to wit:

The study provided a comprehensive assessment of the level of implementation of TVET programs, offering valuable insights into the perspectives of both trainers and trainees. Overall, the findings indicated a positive perception of the program's implementation, with both groups largely agreeing on the "fully implemented" status across various components. However, in the assessment of tools, equipment, and materials revealed slight discrepancies between trainers and

trainees, highlighting potential areas for improvement. Moreover, the identified challenges, including misalignment of curriculum design with local industry needs, limited resources, space constraints, and a shortage of highly qualified trainers, impact the quality and effectiveness of the TVET programs.

Recommendations

In the context of the above enumerated findings and conclusions, the researcher arrived at the following recommendations:

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1. While the TVET programs in Marinduque are largely successful, there are areas that need to be addressed for continuous improvement. By implementing the proposed strategies and taking the necessary steps, it is expected that the quality, relevance, and effectiveness of the TVET programs will be enhanced, ultimately improving the employment prospects of the graduates.
 2. For TVET institution to implement a vigorous monitoring and evaluation system to continuously assess the quality and impact of TVET programs. Collect feedback from trainers, trainees, employers, and other stakeholders to identify areas for improvement and track progress towards program goals and objectives.
 3. Provide training and capacity building opportunities for both trainers and trainees to enhance their skills in using tools, equipment, and materials effectively. Offer workshops, seminars, and hands-on training sessions to familiarize trainers and trainees with the latest technologies and best practices in their respective fields.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

As the author of this study, I affirm that ethical standards were rigorously upheld throughout the research process. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants, emphasizing their voluntary participation and the freedom to withdraw from the study at any point without consequences. The anonymity of the respondents was meticulously preserved to ensure confidentiality and protect their privacy. Measures were taken to safeguard the well-being of the participants, prioritizing their mental and emotional welfare.

Furthermore, I confirm that there is no conflict of interest that could influence the conduct or outcomes of this study. Strict adherence to academic integrity was maintained, with plagiarism vigilantly avoided in all aspects of the research. The interpretation of the findings was approached without bias, ensuring objectivity and reliability in the analysis. The results obtained from this study are solely intended for research purposes, contributing to the advancement of knowledge in the respective field.

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